

Appendix A: Additional Posterior Tables and Figures

For completeness, Tabs. A.1 and A.2 record the outcomes of the standard Bayesian retrieval analysis using BeAR for the orbit-averaged HST spectra from 2018 and 2020, and the corresponding summary of Bayesian statistics, respectively. Fig. A.1 represents the joint posterior distributions from free-chemistry retrieval analyses of the HST 2018 maximum brightness spectrum with a gray-cloud model. Fig. A.2 shows the retrieved atmospheric properties across the 66 different HST spectra from 2018, which are constructed from 6 different orbits of VHS 1256 b. This Figure is analogous to Fig. 4, but fixing the surface gravity value of $\log g = 4.45 \pm 0.03$. In Fig. A.3, the joint posterior distributions from the free-chemistry retrieval analyses of the VLT/X-shooter spectrum taken by Petrus et al. (2023) and using a gray-cloud model is shown. Fig. A.4 then represents the best-fit spectra and posteriors from performing random forest retrievals applied to the JWST spectra of VHS 1256 b, looking at each instrument individually and using the pre-computed model grid BT-Sett1 (Allard et al. 2011).

Table A.1. Summary of orbit-averaged retrieval outcomes for the brown dwarf VHS 1256 b.

Model	Parameter	HST18 ave	HST18 max	HST18 min	HST20 ave	HST20 max	HST20 min
cloud-free	$\log g$ [cm/s ²]	5.37 ^{+0.21} _{-0.32}	5.19 ^{+0.23} _{-0.37}	5.04 ^{+0.22} _{-0.32}	5.02 ^{+0.43} _{-0.75}	5.19 ^{+0.26} _{-0.39}	4.45 ^{+0.70} _{-0.88}
gray	$\log g$ [cm/s ²]	5.67 ^{+0.22} _{-0.31}	5.65 ^{+0.21} _{-0.28}	5.64 ^{+0.21} _{-0.29}	5.41 ^{+0.33} _{-0.55}	4.57 ^{+0.82} _{-0.73}	5.46 ^{+0.27} _{-0.23}
non-gray	$\log g$ [cm/s ²]	5.73 ^{+0.21} _{-0.23}	5.45 ^{+0.21} _{-0.28}	5.33 ^{+0.34} _{-0.35}	5.36 ^{+0.33} _{-0.61}	5.23 ^{+0.28} _{-0.40}	5.30 ^{+0.23} _{-1.36}
cloud-free	R [R _J]	0.76 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.76 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.76 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.78 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.78 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.79 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}
gray	R [R _J]	0.75 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.75 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.75 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.77 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.78 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.77 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}
non-gray	R [R _J]	0.75 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.75 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.75 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.77 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.77 ^{+0.01} _{-0.01}	0.76 ^{+0.02} _{-0.01}
cloud-free	d [pc]	21.17 ^{+0.18} _{-0.20}	21.15 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	21.16 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	21.14 ^{+0.18} _{-0.18}	21.15 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	21.16 ^{+0.16} _{-0.17}
gray	d [pc]	21.15 ^{+0.18} _{-0.18}	21.14 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}	21.13 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}	21.14 ^{+0.18} _{-0.18}	21.14 ^{+0.17} _{-0.17}	21.15 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}
non-gray	d [pc]	21.14 ^{+0.17} _{-0.17}	21.15 ^{+0.17} _{-0.17}	21.15 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}	21.14 ^{+0.17} _{-0.18}	21.14 ^{+0.16} _{-0.16}	21.13 ^{+0.15} _{-0.15}
cloud-free	$\log \text{H}_2\text{O}$	-1.35 ^{+0.23} _{-0.38}	-1.46 ^{+0.29} _{-0.41}	-1.39 ^{+0.24} _{-0.26}	-1.85 ^{+0.53} _{-0.84}	-1.59 ^{+0.32} _{-0.43}	-2.34 ^{+0.80} _{-0.32}
gray	$\log \text{H}_2\text{O}$	-1.74 ^{+0.35} _{-0.28}	-1.61 ^{+0.30} _{-0.30}	-1.61 ^{+0.32} _{-0.32}	-1.69 ^{+0.39} _{-0.60}	-2.53 ^{+0.90} _{-0.75}	-1.69 ^{+0.32} _{-0.38}
non-gray	$\log \text{H}_2\text{O}$	-1.76 ^{+0.24} _{-0.25}	-1.40 ^{+0.24} _{-0.30}	-1.39 ^{+0.23} _{-0.31}	-1.70 ^{+0.41} _{-0.65}	-1.71 ^{+0.34} _{-0.44}	-1.71 ^{+0.27} _{-1.28}
cloud-free	T_{eff} [K]	1368.60 ^{+6.02} _{-7.65}	1382.44 ^{+6.98} _{-9.09}	1360.17 ^{+6.21} _{-7.24}	1381.93 ^{+7.17} _{-11.22}	1387.37 ^{+5.73} _{-8.87}	1370.52 ^{+6.50} _{-10.14}
gray	T_{eff} [K]	1377.48 ^{+6.59} _{-9.52}	1388.52 ^{+6.84} _{-9.98}	1365.97 ^{+5.71} _{-7.46}	1385.26 ^{+6.76} _{-13.31}	1380.35 ^{+10.52} _{-18.38}	1378.29 ^{+4.83} _{-7.43}
non-gray	T_{eff} [K]	1374.62 ^{+6.97} _{-8.58}	1381.85 ^{+6.35} _{-8.04}	1358.98 ^{+5.78} _{-6.37}	1386.35 ^{+6.96} _{-12.10}	1388.52 ^{+5.84} _{-10.05}	1379.32 ^{+6.43} _{-11.67}
cloud-free	$\log p_t$ [bar]	-	-	-	-	-	-
gray	$\log p_t$ [bar]	-0.17 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	-0.14 ^{+0.07} _{-0.08}	-0.18 ^{+0.07} _{-0.07}	-0.16 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	-0.16 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	-0.15 ^{+0.07} _{-0.08}
non-gray	$\log p_t$ [bar]	-0.18 ^{+0.08} _{-0.07}	-0.18 ^{+0.08} _{-0.07}	-0.21 ^{+0.07} _{-0.06}	-0.18 ^{+0.08} _{-0.08}	-0.18 ^{+0.08} _{-0.07}	-0.18 ^{+0.07} _{-0.07}
cloud-free	$\log p_b$ [bar]	-	-	-	-	-	-
gray	$\log p_b$ [bar]	1.27 ^{+0.26} _{-0.31}	1.30 ^{+0.23} _{-0.27}	1.31 ^{+0.23} _{-0.25}	0.96 ^{+0.45} _{-0.45}	0.82 ^{+0.49} _{-0.33}	1.26 ^{+0.26} _{-0.33}
non-gray	$\log p_b$ [bar]	1.36 ^{+0.22} _{-0.28}	1.27 ^{+0.27} _{-0.41}	1.15 ^{+0.36} _{-0.95}	1.15 ^{+0.34} _{-0.41}	1.20 ^{+0.31} _{-0.37}	1.25 ^{+0.28} _{-0.38}
cloud-free	τ	-	-	-	-	-	-
gray	τ	1.94 ^{+0.47} _{-0.42}	1.73 ^{+0.29} _{-0.31}	1.53 ^{+0.32} _{-0.26}	1.99 ^{+0.65} _{-0.74}	2.00 ^{+0.82} _{-0.69}	1.81 ^{+0.37} _{-0.35}
non-gray	τ	3.23 ^{+2.98} _{-1.56}	3.14 ^{+2.95} _{-1.50}	3.22 ^{+2.86} _{-1.54}	3.17 ^{+3.18} _{-1.57}	3.25 ^{+2.90} _{-1.58}	3.15 ^{+2.67} _{-1.46}
cloud-free	$\log Q_0$	-	-	-	-	-	-
gray	$\log Q_0$	-	-	-	-	-	-
non-gray	$\log Q_0$	6.96 ^{+6.83} _{-4.79}	6.00 ^{+5.63} _{-4.17}	6.38 ^{+6.45} _{-4.43}	6.57 ^{+6.93} _{-4.55}	6.13 ^{+6.48} _{-4.24}	5.43 ^{+4.67} _{-3.65}
cloud-free	a_0	-	-	-	-	-	-
gray	a_0	-	-	-	-	-	-
non-gray	a_0	9.55 ^{+25.65} _{-6.91}	10.21 ^{+27.30} _{-7.48}	10.74 ^{+27.94} _{-7.84}	9.95 ^{+29.11} _{-7.40}	9.61 ^{+26.36} _{-6.88}	10.90 ^{+26.08} _{-7.77}
cloud-free	$\log a$ [μm]	-	-	-	-	-	-
gray	$\log a$ [μm]	-	-	-	-	-	-
non-gray	$\log a$ [μm]	0.51 ^{+0.02} _{-0.02}	0.52 ^{+0.06} _{-0.03}	0.54 ^{+0.14} _{-0.04}	0.59 ^{+0.07} _{-0.06}	0.56 ^{+0.06} _{-0.05}	0.52 ^{+0.04} _{-0.02}

Table A.2. Summary of Bayesian statistics for the brown dwarf VHS 1256 b orbit-averaged retrievals.

Model	Parameter	HST18 ave	HST18 max	HST18 min	HST20 ave	HST20 max	HST20 min
cloud-free	evidence	4203.28	4180.01	4205.45	4222.25	4206.07	4225.31
gray	evidence	4213.76	4187.01	4217.81	4225.34	4209.46	4230.59
non-gray	evidence	4207.17	4180.92	4207.09	4223.49	4206.19	4225.51
gray vs. cloud-free	$\ln B_{ij}$	10.48	7.09	12.36	3.09	3.39	5.28
non-gray vs. cloud-free	$\ln B_{ij}$	3.89	0.90	1.64	1.24	0.12	0.20
gray vs. non-gray	$\ln B_{ij}$	6.60	6.19	10.72	1.85	3.27	5.08

Fig. A.1. Joint posterior distributions from free-chemistry retrieval analyses of the HST 2018 maximum brightness spectrum with a gray-cloud model. Note that the surface gravity is retrieved for and not a fixed value. The vertical dashed lines correspond to the median parameter values and their 1σ uncertainties. Accompanying each montage of joint posterior distributions is the retrieved median temperature–pressure profile and its associated 1σ uncertainties. The gray horizontal bar indicated the retrieved cloud pressures (from p_t and p_b). The effective temperature T_{eff} is the only parameter that is determined via post-processing. Additionally, the contribution function is displayed in the top center panel, showing each pressure’s contribution percentage to the flux at each wavelength as black shading.

Fig. A.2. HST18 BeAR posteriors with a fixed surface gravity of $\log g = 4.45 \pm 0.03$ and vertically uniform (left column) vs. non-uniform (right column) H_2O abundances as a sequence over all 6 orbits in 2018. Each orbit consist of 11 intra-orbit spectra. Orbit-averaged posteriors are shown in red. The reduced chi-square values correspond to a fit of a straight line through all posteriors of a given parameter. The lowest panel represents the brightness change in G141 broad band, normalized by $3.0 \times 10^{-13} \text{ erg/s/cm}^2/\mu\text{m}$ (data taken from [Bowler et al. 2020](#) and [Zhou et al. 2022](#)).

Fig. A.3. Joint posterior distributions from free-chemistry retrieval analyses of the VLT/X-shooter spectrum taken by [Petrus et al. \(2023\)](#) with a gray-cloud model. The vertical dashed lines correspond to the median parameter values and their 1σ uncertainties. Accompanying each montage of joint posterior distributions is the retrieved median temperature–pressure profile and its associated 1σ uncertainties. The gray horizontal bar indicated the retrieved cloud pressures (from p_t and p_b). The effective temperature T_{eff} is the only parameter that is determined via post-processing. Additionally, the contribution function is displayed in the top center panel, showing each pressure’s contribution percentage to the flux at each wavelength as black shading.

Fig. A.4. JWST spectra of VHS 1256 b (dark gray dots), overlaid by the BT-Sett1 (Allard et al. 2011) best fit model spectra for each of the 15 independent spectral windows. Corresponding posteriors for effective temperature T_{eff} , surface gravity $\log g$, and scaling factor f are presented in the five lower panels, where the parameter range of the grid itself is indicated by the colored area. The posterior values and corresponding errors when using the entire spectrum are shown by the gray line and shaded gray area, respectively. Dashed lines represent the corresponding averaged values from the machine learning retrievals with HST data (see Fig. 5 and 6).